

CAIRT Phase A Mission Performance and Requirement Consolidation (PerReC) Activity

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CAIRT linear SWB ATBD

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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>CAIRT Phase A mission performance evaluation relies primarily on a set of tools bundled into the Scientific Workbench (SWB). These tools are used for (1) deriving L1b requirements from L2a requirements, (2) establishing comprehensive and rigorous L2a product uncertainty budgets, considering all relevant error propagation pathways from L1 to L2, (3) evaluating performance of L2b products, and (4) generating extensive datasets of emulated L2a data products for scientific impact studies. A schematic overview of the SWB is provided in Figure 1. Note that L2b performance estimation tools required for (3) are described in a separate ATBD document.</p>		
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides with the author(s) or organisation(s) that prepared it.</p>		
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uncertainty assessment based either on Gaussian error propagation (or Law of Propagation of Uncertainties), via the error covariance, or based on Monte Carlo Analysis, via an ensemble of perturbation responses. Error propagation through the sequential L2 chain is relevant for the impact of temperature and line-of-sight (LOS) pointing uncertainties on subsequent retrievals, while it can be efficiently suppressed for trace gas retrieval errors via appropriate selection of spectral windows. Therefore, the LPE considers uncertainty propagation of L1 and atmospheric uncertainties through retrieved temperature and LOS onto subsequent trace gas retrievals, following the approach applied in MIPAS error reporting [3]. A limitation of the LPE is that there is no tomographic retrieval approach for evaluating temporally uncorrelated uncertainties beyond measurement noise. Such uncertainties, like pointing jitter, are therefore evaluated by means of 1D retrieval simulations.

The *Scene generator* produces realistic high-resolution atmospheric scenes, i.e. discrete representations of the state of the atmosphere covering relevant physical quantities such as temperature, pressure, trace gas volume mixing ratios, cloud optical depth, etc., on the CAIRT L2 retrieval grid for a given observation geometry of the satellite. These scenes are the required input for the L2b Performance estimator and for L2a data emulation with the FL2S (see below) for scientific impact studies. This purpose is achieved with the Scene generator module (SGM) developed in the framework of CEEPS, allowing for generation of scene data fully compatible with the FL2S input requirements. A detailed documentation of the CAIRTS SGM can be found in GMV-CEEPS-TN2-Models-ATBD. Therefore, no alternative scene generator has been developed within the PerReC project. However, a dedicated CAIRT retrieval grid generator (*sim_CAIRT_grid*), based on a full year of CAIRT orbit data, has been developed and is described in Sec. 6. This generator was used in most scientific impact studies for the generation of the retrieval grid. Interpolation of model data onto the generated retrieval grid was done with impact study-specific approaches as described in the corresponding README files D-14-1 to D-14-6.

The *Fast Level-2 Simulator (FL2S)* is the main tool for emulation of CAIRT L2a data used in science impact assessments. The FL2S selects and interpolates 2D averaging kernels and estimated error terms, which have been computed with the LPE from the ERS climatology, to each of the scene grid points and executes the respective convolution. This emulates a computationally efficient parametric retrieval response for the scene. MC-derived calibration errors are randomly selected from the perturbation response ensemble for each assumed calibration period. Measurement noise errors are obtained from the decomposition of the noise error covariance, and subsequently multiplied with a random vector, thus fully accounting for correlations between retrieval grid points. Within the performance evaluation, FL2S is used to showcase performance on realistic model input datasets and to provide input data for L2b performance estimation. It is further used to generate validation test datasets to be compared to CEEPS results.

2 The Extended Reference Scenario ERS

The construction of the ERS is outlined in [4]. This climatology was constructed from averaged atmospheric conditions that encompass the full range of expected seasonal, latitudinal and diurnal variations to be measured by CAIRT. ERS are provided as multiannual monthly mean profiles for January, April, July and October in five latitude bands (90°S-70°S, 55°S-35°S, $\pm 20^\circ$, 35°N-55°N and 70°N-90°N) and for all relevant trace gases. For short-lived species, ERS are averaged at the morning (9:30) and afternoon (21:30) of the overpass time. ERS profiles were used for L2a requirement consolidation, as well as for establishing complete uncertainty budgets and spatial resolution assessments within the SWB- based performance evaluation. ERS are also used in CEEPS for simplified tests. The dataset is publicly available here:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10022129> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8256025>

3 The spectra and Jacobian database (SJD)

On basis of the (nlte-extended) ERS, the Spectra and Jacobian Database (SJD) has been produced using the line-by-line radiative transfer model KOPRA (CAIRT_KOPRA_ATBD).

It constitutes of a selection of broad-band (covering the spectral range of CAIRT) radiance spectra as well as their Jacobians with respect to retrieval parameters. These parameters are temperature and volume mixing ratios of trace gases either at different altitude levels to support 1d-retrievals or a at different altitude and latitude levels as basis for the 2d retrievals). Further, the SJD includes error disturbance spectra for a variety of non-LTE parameters [5] as well as the CO₂-profile.

In detail, the SJD contains limb radiances, radiance derivatives and radiance perturbances calculated with the KOPRA radiative transfer model as ‘pencil beams’, i.e. for an infinitesimal field-of-view. The tangent altitudes of the pencil beams with a spacing of 0.5 km from 0.5 km to 125 km cover well the CAIRT vertical observational range. In the spectral domain, the ‘monochromatic’ radiances are sampled at a wavenumber grid of 0.1 cm⁻¹ by use of a sinc-function, corresponding to the goal spectral resolution of CAIRT. These settings allow for a use of the SJD spectra in the instrument model for geometrical field-of-view and spectral AILS convolution for any of the CAIRT geometric and spectral requirements.

The atmospheric parameters are discretized at horizontal and vertical levels (for which the Jacobians have been calculated) with a 0.5 km grid distance in the vertical and 50 km distance in the horizontal. Horizontal 2d-fields are constructed from the ERS by repetition of the same ERS altitude profiles over a horizontal region such that it contains the entire limb-paths. The ERS atmospheric scenarios have been used to map a large part of the atmospheric variability.

2d Jacobians are calculated for the following parameters in non-LTE:

- Temperature, H₂O, O₃, CO, CH₄, NO, NO₂, gray-body extinction, and in LTE for targets in the ‘lower’ atmosphere where non-LTE effects can be neglected:
- C₂H₂, C₂H₆, CFC-11, CFC-12, ClONO₂, HCN, HCOOH, HNO₃, N₂O, N₂O₅, NH₃, PAN, SF₆, SO₂, H₂SO₄-liq, NH₄NO₃-sld.

Jacobians for spectral shift, i.e. a shift in the spectral axis to simulated spectral calibration errors, are also determined already at this stage because the reduction of the spectra by the sinc-function convolution impedes a determination of spectral shift-derivatives within the instrument simulator.

The total disc space occupied by the SJD is currently around 2 TB.

Figure 2: Example for one file of the SJD.

Table 1: Ncdump of one file header of the SJD.

```

netcdf Y:\cairt\sirec\Data\V2nlte_2d\EE11_Jacobians_V2nlte_2d_all_july+45_ngt_mw_00.nc {
  dimensions:
    wavenumber = 261;
    htang = 245;
    hlev = 260;
    latlev = 73;
    indlev = 140800;
  variables:
    double wavenumber(wavenumber=261);
    
```

```

:units = "cm-1";
:long_name = "Wavenumber";
float htang(htang=245);
:units = "km";
:long_name = "Tangent altitude";
float hnadir(htang=245);
:units = "rad";
:long_name = "Nadir angle";
float hlev(hlev=260);
:units = "km";
:long_name = "Parameter level altitude";
float latlev(latlev=73);
:units = "degrees_north";
:long_name = "Parameter level latitude";
long indlev(indlev=140800);
:long_name = "Parameter level index";
:units = "";
long indgeo(indlev=140800);
:units = "";
:long_name = "Geometry index";
float rad(htang=245, wavenumber=261);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)";
:long_name = "Radiance";

float drad(indlev=140800, wavenumber=261);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1/K)";
:long_name = "Radiance derivatives";
float dshirad(htang=245, wavenumber=261);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)/cm-1";
:long_name = "Radiance wavenumber shift derivatives";
float ptang(htang=245);
:units = "hPa";
:long_name = "Tangent pressure";
float Ttang(htang=245);
:units = "K";
:long_name = "Tangent temperature";
float vmrtang(htang=245);
:units = "ppmv";
:long_name = "Tangent volume mixing ratio";
float p_lev(hlev=260);
:units = "hPa";
:long_name = "Level pressure";
float T_lev(hlev=260);
:units = "K";
:long_name = "Level temperature";
float vmr_lev(hlev=260);
:units = "ppmv";
:long_name = "Level volume mixing ratio";
// global attributes:
:Description = "Radiance spectra and radiance Jacobian spectra: radiance derivatives per level change (triangular change up to next profile level in radiance units per ppmv for gas and per Kelvin for temperature derivatives)";
:Author = "Michael Hoepfner, michael.hoepfner@kit.edu";
:Version = "1";
:KOPRA_version = "8.4.4";
:vmr_file = "/home/hoepfner/Projects/ESA_EE11/Forward_Jacobis/Ref_files/ERS_v7/july+45_ngt_vmr.prf";
:pT_file = "/home/hoepfner/Projects/ESA_EE11/Forward_Jacobis/Ref_files/ERS_v7/july+45_ngt_pt.prf";
:Species = "T";
:MOPD = "5 cm";
:Apodization = "Sinc";
>Date = "20221219-012831";
}

```

4 The L1b Simulator

The L1b simulator module reads the SJD files and applies vertical convolution to account for the vertical sampling and field-of-view (SEDF) as well as spectral convolution to account for the spectral sampling and apodized instrumental line shape (AILS or AISRF). This is done for all the Jacobians as well as error spectra already contained in the SJD. Furthermore, the instrument simulator determines new Jacobians with respect to vertical pointing, as well as error spectra regarding the knowledge of the vertical field-of-view (SEDF) and the knowledge of the ILS (ISRF). For a detailed listing of the instrumental uncertainties as well as the uncertainties from the SJD we refer to the chapters 'Instrument simulation' and 'Linear performance estimation' in [6].

4.1 Application of the AILS

The spectra and Jacobians of the SJD are pure ‘sinc’ spectra, i.e. not apodized nor any instrumental line-shape has been applied to them. The L1b simulator convolves these spectra with the Norton-Beer-Strong apodization function [7], [8], Table 2:

$$S_{\theta}^{AILS}(v) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{\theta}(v') AILS(v - v') dv' \tag{1}$$

S_{θ}	spectral radiance for viewing angle θ
$AILS$	Instrument line-shape incl. numerical apodization (apodized instrumental line shape)

To calculate Eq. (1), discrete linear convolution is performed (using the python routine numpy.convolve):

$$S_{\theta}^{AILS}(v_n) = \sum_{m=-m_0}^{m_0} S_{\theta}(v_m) AILS(v_n - v_m) \tag{2}$$

m_0 is determined by the size of the truncation window which can be configured to ensure that the ‘transmission’ $T = AILS(v)/AILS(0)$ from outside the window is lower than a certain threshold. In case of Norton-Beer strong: $T = 0.01$ for $v=1.5/MOPD$, $T = 0.001$ for $v=14/MOPD$, $T = 0.0001$ for $v=140/MOPD$ where MOPD denotes the maximum optical path difference [cm].

Table 2 The Norton-Beer apodization.

<p>Norton-Beer apodization from [7]:</p> <p>Because the apodizing functions $FN(U)$ are expressed as power series, the terms are separable and the ILS are readily derived as</p> $IN(\sigma) = \sum_{i=0}^n C_i Q_i, \quad N=0, 1, 2, 3$ <p>where</p> $Q_0 = \text{sinc } a,$ $Q_1 = \frac{3(\text{sinc } a - \text{cosa})}{a^2},$ $Q_2 = \frac{-15[(1 - 3/a^2)\text{sinc } a + (3/a^2)\text{cosa}]}{a^2},$ $Q_3 = \frac{105[(1 - 15/a^2)\text{cosa} + 3(2 - 5/a^2)\text{sinc } a]}{a^4},$ $Q_4 = \frac{945[(1 - 45/a^2 + 105/a^4)\text{sinc } a + 5/a^2(2 - 21/a^2)\text{cosa}]}{a^4},$ <p>$a = 2\pi\sigma L$.</p> <p>Note that, since $C_3 \equiv 0$ for all the functions, Q_3 plays no role in the evaluation but is included for completeness.</p> <p>The expressions for the Q_i are accurate but tend to</p>		<p>be numerically unstable for values of a less than about 0.7. For small arguments, it is better to use the expansions</p> $Q'_0 = 1 - \frac{a^2}{6} + \frac{a^4}{120} - \frac{a^6}{5040} + \frac{a^8}{362880} - \dots,$ $Q'_1 = 1 - \frac{a^2}{10} + \frac{a^4}{280} - \frac{a^6}{15120} + \frac{a^8}{1330560} - \dots,$ $Q'_2 = 1 - \frac{a^2}{14} + \frac{a^4}{504} - \frac{a^6}{33264} + \frac{a^8}{3459456} - \dots,$ $Q'_3 = 1 - \frac{a^2}{18} + \frac{a^4}{792} - \frac{a^6}{61776} + \frac{a^8}{7413120} - \dots,$ $Q'_4 = 1 - \frac{a^2}{22} + \frac{a^4}{1144} - \frac{a^6}{102960} + \frac{a^8}{14002560} - \dots,$ <p>which are accurate to $< 10^{-9}$ for $a < 0.7$.</p>
---	--	---

Mind the erratum [8]:

R. H. Norton and R. Beer, "New apodizing functions for Fourier spectrometry,"
 p. 261: The expressions for the Q_i and the Q'_i should be changed as follows:

- Q_1 and Q'_1 should be multiplied by 2/3,
- Q_2 and Q'_2 should be multiplied by 8/15,
- Q_3 and Q'_3 should be multiplied by 48/105,
- Q_4 and Q'_4 should be multiplied by 384/945.

p. 261: Table I should be replaced in its entirety by

Apodizing function number	C_0	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	Comments
0	1	0	0	0	0	No apodization
1	0.384093	-0.087577	0.703484	0	0	"Weak" apodization
2	0.152442	-0.136176	0.983734	0	0	"Medium" apodization
3	0.045335	0	0.554883	0	0.399782	"Strong" apodization

4.2 Application of the vertical SEDF

After the convolution with the AILS, the vertical SEDF is applied to all spectra, Jacobian spectra, and error spectra by:

$$S_{x_0}^{SEDF}(\nu) = \int_{-x_{max}}^{x_{max}} S_x^{AILS}(\nu) SEDF(\nu, x, x - x_0) dx \quad (3)$$

with:

$SEDF(\nu, x_0, x - x_0)$	weighting function related (vertical) SEDF
$S_{x_0}^{SEDF}$	SEDF-convolved spectral radiance and Jacobians for viewing angle x_0
S_x^{AILS}	spectral radiance for infinitesimal viewing angle x convolved by apodized instrumental line shape
ν	wavenumber (wavenumber) [cm^{-1}]
x	viewing angle (vertical)
x_{max}	maximum angle covered by the SEDF

The SEDF-shape is flexibly implemented such that it can be dependent on wavenumber as well as on vertical pixel position. Numerically, the integration is performed by linear interpolation of the limb-radiances to the vertical grid points of the SEDF function. Then the multiplication of the two functions and the addition is performed. This procedure can be optimized in future versions of the code, since the vertical variability of the radiance and its gridding (of about 0.5 km) is generally smaller than that of the SEDF function. To optimize, one would first integrate the SEDF function to the grid-distance of the radiance and then perform the summation.

Different versions of the SEDF function are implemented:

4.2.1 User-supplied SEDF

In that case, a realistic SEDF function is read from a netcdf-file. This function can vary with wavenumber. The form of the file is illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3: Example of a netcdf file format for the user-supplied SEDF.

```
netcdf Y:\cairt\scirec\git\instsim\CSB_sedf_band1_update20250320.nc {
  dimensions:
    n_points_SEDF_ele = 121;
    n_SEDF_sp = 21;
  variables:
    double SEDF(n_points_SEDF_ele=121, n_SEDF_sp=21);
      :description = "System global SEDF";
      :units = "-";
      :_ChunkSizes = 121U, 21U; // uint

    double wavenumber(n_SEDF_sp=21);
      :description = "Wavenumber axis";
      :units = "cm-1";
      :_ChunkSizes = 21U; // uint

    double SEDF_coord_ele(n_points_SEDF_ele=121);
      :description = "Coordinates of the elevation axis of the SEDF";
      :units = "deg";
      :_ChunkSizes = 121U; // uint

  // global attributes:
}
```

4.2.2 Internal SEDF

Apart from a user-supplied external SEDF, an internally calculated SEDF model can be applied. This vertical SEDF model, concatenates a Gaussian curve in the near-field (the inner $SEDF_i$) with a diffraction model (consistent with rectangular instrument aperture) plus a constant value for simulation of scattered radiation in the far-field (the outer $SEDF_o$):

$$SEDF(x) = \begin{cases} SEDF_i(x) = \exp\left(-\ln 2 \left(\frac{2x}{FWHM}\right)^2\right), & |x| < x_0 \\ SEDF_o(x) = \frac{\text{sinc}^2(\pi\sigma D_x \sin x) \otimes \Pi\left(\frac{x}{W}\right)}{\int_{-W/2}^{+W/2} \text{sinc}^2(\pi\sigma D_x \sin x) dx} + sc, & |x| \geq x_0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where x [rad] is the elevation angle, D_x [cm] an assumed aperture height, σ [cm⁻¹] the wavenumber, W [rad] the size of the (sub-)sample, $FWHM$ [rad] the Full Width at Half Maximum of the Gaussian, $\Pi(x/W)$ is

a rectangular function of width W , x_0 is the boundary between inner and outer SEDF, and sc is the scattering contribution. The denominator in $SEDF_o(x)$ normalises the function to one. Conversion between the elevation angle x [rad] and the projected vertical distance around a geometric tangent point follows from simple trigonometry:

$$\begin{aligned} dh[\text{rad}] \text{ (e.g. } x[\text{rad}], FWHM[\text{rad}], x_0[\text{rad}], W[\text{rad}]) &= \\ &= dhtang2elev(H_{sat}, H_{T,ref}, dh[\text{km}]) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} dhtang2elev(H_{sat}, H_T, dh) &= \\ htang2elev(H_{sat}, H_T + dh/2) - htang2elev(H_{sat}, H_T - dh/2) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

and:

$$htang2elev(H_{sat}, H_T) = \text{asin}\left(\frac{R_E + H_T}{R_E + H_{sat}}\right) - \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (7)$$

where:

$R_E = 6367.4445$ km, mean Earth radius

$H_{sat} = 800$ km, satellite altitude (configurable)

$FWHM[\text{km}]$ =FWHM of the SEDF in km (configurable)

$x_0[\text{km}]$ =half extension of inner SEDF (configurable)

$W[\text{km}]$ = width of the pixel for which the SEDF applies (configurable)

Figure 3 Example for a vertical SEDF as vertical distance around the tangent point, including the far-field (blue, in log-scale) and focused around the nearest neighbours (orange, in linear scale); here, $x_0 \sim 1.5$ km, FWHM = 1.5 km, $D_x = 4$ cm, $W = 1$ km. For no scattering contribution ($sc = 0$).

Figure 4 Same as Figure 3 but including a scattering contribution of $sc = 10^{-5}$.

4.3 Calculation of perturbation- and LOS-derivative-spectra

Please mind in the following that the provided numbers are used to determine derivatives by adding ‘small’ deviations to the parameters. Since we assume linear error estimation, these ‘Jacobians’ are scaled to the values used in the requirement deviation and performance assessments. The related numbers are provided e.g. in chapter ‘Linear performance evaluation’ in [6].

4.3.1 AILS

Perturbation of the AILS is simulated numerically by changing the width of the AILS function by 1% (configurable), recalculating the spectra with this perturbed AILS and, after application of the SEDF, calculation of the difference to the reference spectra.

4.3.2 SEDF near-field

Perturbation of the near-field SEDF is simulated numerically by changing the $FWHM_{km}$ of the Gaussian by 1% (configurable), recalculating the spectra with this perturbed SEDF and calculation of the difference to the reference spectra.

4.3.3 SEDF far-field

To simulate the effect of the knowledge uncertainties of the far-field diffraction/scattering pattern on the retrieval, numerical Jacobian spectra are calculated by perturbing different vertical regions of the far-filed SEDF function. The number and positions of the different regions as well as the values of perturbation are configurable. This is illustrated in Figure 5 for the regions 1.5-2.5 km, 2.5-5.5 km, 5.5-20.5 km, 20.5-60.5 km, and 60.5-117.5 km.

Figure 5: Example for a possible perturbation of the far-field vertical SEDF.

4.3.4 Line-of-sight elevation derivative

Jacobian spectra with respect to the line-of-sight are numerically determined by application of a vertically shifted SEDF to the reference spectra:

$$\frac{\partial S_{x_0}^{SEDF}(\nu)}{\partial x_0} \cong \frac{S_{x_0+\Delta x_0}^{SEDF}(\nu) - S_{x_0}^{SEDF}(\nu)}{\Delta x_0} \quad (8)$$

4.4 The instrument-simulated spectra and Jacobian database (iSJD)

Output spectra, Jacobians, and uncertainty spectra as calculated by the instrument simulator are provided as netcdf-files (see Figure 6 and Table 4).

Name	Long Name	Type
EE11_Jacobians_ILS_opd25mm_FOV_V2nlte_2d_all_april+00_mw_00.nc	EE11_Jacobians_ILS_opd25mm_FOV_V2nlte_2d_all_april+00_mw_00.nc	Local File
ddiffrafovcrad	Radiance SEDF combined ranges perturbed	2D
ddiffrastrayfovcrad	Radiance SEDF single ranges perturbed	2D
dfov2crad	Radiance SEDF combined ranges perturbed	2D
dfovcrad	Radiance FOV constant width perturbed	2D
dfovrrad	Radiance FOV random width perturbed	2D
dilsrad	Radiance ILS perturbed	2D
dlosrad	Radiance LOS derivative	2D
drad	Radiance derivatives	2D
dshirad	Radiance wavenumber shift derivatives	2D
dstrayfovcrad	Radiance SEDF combined ranges perturbed	2D
hlev	Parameter level altitude	1D
hnadir	Nadir angle	1D
htang	Tangent altitude not refracted	1D
htang_refra	Tangent altitude refracted	1D
indgeo	Geometry index	1D
indlev	Parameter level index	1D
latlev	Parameter level latitude	1D
p_lev	Level pressure	1D
rad	Radiance	2D
T_lev	Level temperature	1D
vmr_lev	Level volume mixing ratio	1D
wavenumber	Wavenumber	1D

Figure 6 Example of output file variables of the instrument simulator containing the iSJD.

Table 4: Ncdump of an output file of the instrument simulator containing the iSJD.

```
netcdf Y:\cairt\scirec\Data\V2nlte_2d_ILS_opd25mm_diffrastrayerr\EE11_Jacobians_ILS_opd25mm_FOV_V2nlte_2d_all_april+00_mw_00.nc {
  dimensions:
    hlev = 260;
    latlev = 73;
    wavenumber = 107;
    htang = 115;
    indlev = 90182;
    idiffrrange = 5;
    ifovrnd = 10;
  variables:
    float hlev(hlev=260);
      :long_name = "Parameter level altitude";
      :units = "km";
    float latlev(latlev=73);
      :units = "degrees_north";
      :long_name = "Parameter level latitude";
    float p_lev(hlev=260);
      :units = "hPa";
```

```

:long_name = "Level pressure";
float T_lev(hlev=260);
:units = "K";
:long_name = "Level temperature";
float vmr_lev(hlev=260);
:units = "ppmv";
:long_name = "Level volume mixing ratio";
double wavenumber(wavenumber=107);
:units = "cm-1";
:long_name = "Wavenumber";
float htang(htang=115);
:units = "km";
:long_name = "Tangent altitude not refracted";
float htang_refra(htang=115);
:units = "km";
:long_name = "Tangent altitude refracted";
float hnadir(htang=115);
:units = "rad";
:long_name = "Nadir angle";

long indlev(indlev=90182);
:units = "";
:long_name = "Parameter level index";
long indgeo(indlev=90182);
:units = "";
:long_name = "Geometry index";
float rad(htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)";
:long_name = "Radiance";
float drad(indlev=90182, wavenumber=107);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)/K";
:long_name = "Radiance derivatives";
float dshirad(htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)/cm-1";
:long_name = "Radiance wavenumber shift derivatives";
float dlosrad(htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)/rad";
:long_name = "Radiance LOS derivative";
float ddiffrastrayfovcrad(idiffrange=5, htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)";
:long_name = "Radiance SEDF single ranges perturbed";
float dfov2crad(htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:ranges = "[[ 1.5 2.5]]";
:ptb_values = "[[ 0.01]]";
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)";
:long_name = "Radiance SEDF combined ranges perturbed";
float ddiffrafovcrad(htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:ptb_values = "[[ 5.30000000e-04 6.10000000e-05]]";
:ranges = "[[ 2.5 5.5]\n [ 5.5 20.5]]";
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)";
:long_name = "Radiance SEDF combined ranges perturbed";
float dstrayfovcrad(htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:ranges = "[[ 20.5 60.5]\n [ 60.5 117.5]]";
:ptb_values = "[[ 1.20000000e-05 5.00000000e-06]]";
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)";
:long_name = "Radiance SEDF combined ranges perturbed";
float dfovcrad(htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)";
:long_name = "Radiance FOV constant width perturbed";
float dfovrrad(fovrrnd=10, htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)";
:long_name = "Radiance FOV random width perturbed";
float dilsrad(htang=115, wavenumber=107);
:units = "nW/(cm2 sr cm-1)";
:long_name = "Radiance ILS perturbed";
// global attributes:
:Author = "Michael Hoepfner, michael.hoepfner@kit.edu";
:Version = "1";
:KOPRA_version = "8.4.4";
:vmr_file = "/home/hoepfner/Projects/ESA_EE11/Forward_Jacobis/Ref_files/ERS_v7/april+00_vmr.prf";
:pT_file = "/home/hoepfner/Projects/ESA_EE11/Forward_Jacobis/Ref_files/ERS_v7/april+00_pt.prf";
:Species = "T";
:Description = "Radiance spectra and radiance Jacobian spectra: radiance derivatives per level change (triangular change up to next profile level in radiance units per ppmv for gas and per Kelvin for temperature derivatives)";
:MOPD = "25mm";
:Apodization = "Norton Beer strong";
>Date = "20241220-180554";
:Description2 = "With AILS and vertical FOV (no diffraction) convolved";
}

```


5 The linear performance estimator (LPE)

Following [9], the 2D Linear Performance Estimator (LPE, current version 3 used in Phase A performance evaluations) computes the retrieval covariance matrix \mathbf{S} and the averaging kernel \mathbf{A}

$$\mathbf{S} = [(\sum_i \mathbf{K}_i^T \mathbf{S}_y^{-1} \mathbf{K}_i) + \mathbf{R}]^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{S} (\sum_i \mathbf{K}_i^T \mathbf{S}_y^{-1} \mathbf{K}_i) \quad (10)$$

based on the pre-calculated Jacobians \mathbf{K} from the iSD database in dependence of the assumed regularization (expressed as regularization matrix \mathbf{R}) and the noise covariance matrix \mathbf{S}_y . The sum in Equations (9) and (10) goes over all m along-track observations i included in the 2D retrieval. \mathbf{S}_y is computed from the wavenumber-dependent NESR estimates. Note that \mathbf{S}_y is non-diagonal because of the applied NBS apodization.

For the 2D tomographic retrieval simulations, m is set to 77 (corresponding to an along-track coverage of the LOS extension passing through the entire atmosphere at 200 km altitude). The dimension of the parameter space is $n = m n_z$ with n_z being the number of vertical profile points. The number of along-track parameters is equal to the number of along-track observations. The Jacobian matrix of measurement i with respect to the along-track parameters j (note that for each j there are n_z vertical parameters) are computed as $\mathbf{K}_{i,j} = \mathbf{K}_{i',j'}$ where i' corresponds to the along-track center measurement (for which the KOPRA Jacobian is actually calculated) and $j' = j + i - i'$. That is, the Jacobian is shifted in dependence of the along-track displacement of measurement i with respect to the along-track center measurement. It also implies that \mathbf{K}_i is assumed to be independent on along-track variations of the atmospheric state. This is a reasonable assumption for sensitivity assessments under consideration of climatological mean state conditions.

The estimated standard deviations (ESD) of the L2 measurement noise errors ϵ_{noise} are computed from the noise error covariance matrix

$$\mathbf{S}_m = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{S} \quad (11)$$

The LPEv2 provides ESD for the parameters j' (a vertical profile of dimension n_z) at the along-track center (variable *esd_noise* in Figure 7).

Spatial and temporal correlations of measurement noise errors ϵ_{noise} need to be considered in the FL2S. This is estimated via factorisation of the retrieval measurement covariance matrix \mathbf{S}_m :

$$\epsilon_{\text{noise}} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{r} \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{S}_m = \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{U}, \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{r} is a normalized random vector spanning the parameter space, and \mathbf{U} is computed from \mathbf{S}_m by means of Cholesky decomposition. The LPEv2 provides the matrix elements $U_{j',j}$ corresponding to the parameters j' at the along-track center (variable *correlated noise* in Figure 7), a $n_z \times m$ matrix.

Error propagation of temperature and LOS measurement noise errors onto constituent retrievals (see [4], Section 7.2 therein) is considered by the additional term

$$\mathbf{S}'_m = \mathbf{S} \mathbf{V} \mathbf{S}_m^{\text{tem+LOS}} \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{S}^T \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{S}_m^{\text{tem+LOS}}$ is the noise error covariance matrix of the preceding temperature and LOS joint retrieval, and

$$\mathbf{V} = \sum_i \mathbf{K}_i^T \mathbf{S}_y^{-1} \mathbf{K}_i^{\text{tem+LOS}} \quad (14)$$

is an auxiliary matrix in the parameter space with $\mathbf{K}_i^{\text{tem+LOS}}$ being the Jacobians with respect to temperature and LOS for the spectral windows used in the constituent retrieval [3]. Note that \mathbf{K}_i^T refers here to the transposed Jacobian of the target constituent. The latter is taken again from the iSJD database. For constituent retrievals, the LPEv2 provides the ESD of propagated measurement noise from the temperature and LOS retrieval for the parameters j' (a vertical profile of dimension n_z) at the along-track center (variable *esd_noise_tlos* in Figure 7). In this case, the propagated noise error contribution is also considered as additional term in the computation of the correlated noise by means of Eq. (12).

Error propagation from other sources than measurement noise (e.g., calibration uncertainties, systematic instrumental uncertainties, non-LTE uncertainties) is estimated as

$$\epsilon_{\text{sys}} = -\mathbf{S} (\sum_i \mathbf{K}_i^T \mathbf{S}_y^{-1}) \Delta \mathbf{y} = -\mathbf{G} \Delta \mathbf{y} \quad \text{with } \mathbf{G} = \mathbf{S} (\sum_i \mathbf{K}_i^T \mathbf{S}_y^{-1}) \quad (15)$$

from pre-calculated spectral perturbations $\Delta \mathbf{y}$. These are either provided by the iSJD database or, in the case of calibration errors (radiometric scaling and additive uncertainties), are computed internally. Note that Eq. (15) assumes that the spectral perturbations are the same for all along-track measurements i . This assumption is justified for all temporally correlated errors (including calibration errors if the measurements i correspond to the same calibration period). The LPE provides ϵ_{sys} for the parameters j' (a vertical profile of dimension n_z) at the along-track center (variable *sys_<error source>* in Figure 7). Assuming that all error contributions are uncorrelated, the total systematic uncertainty is estimated as the square root of the quadratic sum of all systematic uncertainty contributions (variable *sys_total* in Fig. 3). Note that *sys_total* in the LPE output netcdf file also accounts for calibration uncertainties.

In the case of spatially uncorrelated uncertainties, Monte Carlo (MC) simulations with random spectral perturbations $\Delta \mathbf{y}$ are performed. For radiometric calibration errors these perturbations are computed by multiplicatively or additively perturbing the reference spectrum with random vectors reflecting the spatial and spectral correlations to be considered. The spectral correlation width is user-defined. The MC ensemble size for these types of errors is use-defined (typically 100). For pointing (relative/absolute) and spectral position errors, $\Delta \mathbf{y}$ is computed from the LOS and spectral shift Jacobians provided by the iSJD. 10 MC perturbation spectra are constructed randomly considering the desired degree of spatial or spectral correlation. Then, ϵ_{sys} refers to the geometric average of all MC members. The LPE also provides the total systematic error corresponding to individual MC members (variable *sys_tot_sample* in Figure 7), which is required by the FL2S in order to simulate the impact of different calibration periods.

In trace gas retrievals, the errors from other uncertainty sources than measurement noise always includes the impact of temperature and LOS error propagation associated to the same uncertainty source. That is, Eq. (15) is then modified to

$$\epsilon_{\text{sys}} = -\mathbf{G} (\Delta\mathbf{y} + \mathbf{V} \epsilon_{\text{sys_tem+LOS}}) \tag{16}$$

with \mathbf{V} from Eq. (14) and $\epsilon_{\text{sys_tem+LOS}}$ being the temperature and LOS error introduced by the same uncertainty source. Note that the consideration of temperature and LOS error propagation can lead to error compensation in case of spectrally correlated uncertainties or amplification in the case of spectrally uncorrelated uncertainties (see [3], for a detailed discussion).

Figure 7 Output file of the LPEv2 for ozone retrieval characteristics.

6 CAIRT retrieval grid generation

The simulation of the CAIRT orbit was carried out taking as a reference the MetOp-SG orbit specifications (IASI-NG) and adjusting the longitude of the ascending node (ANX), in order to match the expected IASI-NG/CAIRT orbit phasing (see Table below).

	Metop-SG	CAIRT
Mean Local Solar Time at ANX	21:30	21:30
repeat cycle [days]	29	29
cycle length [orbits]	412	412
Longitude of ANX [deg]	0.0	1.956721

The CAIRT orbit specifications were written to an Orbit Scenario File (ESA 2021, EOP-PE CFI Team, "Earth Observation Mission Software File Format Specification", Reference PE-ID-ESA-GS-584, Issue 1, Revision 7, Date of Issue 22-12-2021), which is then given as input of a propagation tool (developed in C++ and based on ESA's EO-CFI libraries) to produce a simulated CAIRT orbit. The provided CAIRT orbit propagation starts at 2020-06-30T21:22:12 UTC and consists of the satellite position in the ECEF frame, geodetic coordinates of sub-satellite point and satellite height (more details in the table below) given with a propagation step of 7.56 seconds which correspond approximately to 50 km ALT.

Propagated parameter	Units
date/time UTC	e.g. 2020-06-30T21:30:01.000
satellite position ECEF (x,y,z)	[m]
satellite velocity ECEF (x,y,z)	[m/s]
sub-satellite point latitude, longitude (geodetic)	[deg]
satellite height (geodetic)	[m]

The orbit data are written to a text file, where each line contains the values of a single propagation epoch, as in the example below:

```
2020-06-30T21:30:01.000,7201364.423843,449.543709,-2003.738802,-6.338179,-1650.313376,7355.901010,-0.016037,0.003577,823227.718
```

Providing the position and velocity vectors of the satellite, the second step is to setup the CAIRT measurement and retrieval grids. Leveraging this information, 3D rectilinear grids following the orbit (with x being the along-track dimension, y being the across-track dimension and z being the altitude dimension) are generated. Each x/y-profile is associated with a longitude/latitude/time coordinate.

7 The fast level2 simulator (FL2S)

The FL2S selects and interpolates 2D averaging kernels and estimated error terms to each of the scene grid points and executes the respective convolution resulting in the parametrically retrieved simulated view of the scene, allowing a computationally efficient simulation of the CAIRT retrieval response for a given L2 product. This python tool selects or interpolates 2D averaging kernel row sub-matrices \mathbf{A}_i (a matrix of the dimension $n_z \times m \times n_z$) and error responses corresponding to the along-track center position i , from 2D linear retrieval simulations performed with the LPE for each of the ERS scenarios (defined by season, latitude, illumination, and solar activity conditions) to the actual atmospheric conditions of the model field at the scene grid points. The model field is then convolved with averaging kernels sub-matrices in order to emulate the CAIRT retrieval response. Finally, the simulated error responses are added.

Input to the FL2S is the scene data produced by the scene generator and the LPE output files for the L2 product under consideration (see Figure 7) containing the entire ERS climatology of 2D averaging kernel row sub-matrices (variable *ak2d*), decomposed correlated noise error terms \mathbf{U} (variable *correlated_noise*, see Eq. (12)), and total the systematic error corresponding to individual MC members (variables *sys_tot_sample_corr* and *sys_tot_sample_uncorr*). There are mainly three steps operated in FL2S described in the following subsections.

7.1 Across track binning of input scene

First, the input scenes, given on a 500 km swath and a 25 km ACT resolution, are rebinned on the CAIRT L2 grid with a 400 km swath and 100 km ACT resolution. Assuming the track indices of the input scenes are from $i=1, \dots, 20$, FL2S does remove the tracks 1, 2, 19 and 20. Then, assuming that the L2 tracks are from $j=1, \dots, 4$, FL2S averages the tracks $i3, \dots, i6 \Rightarrow j1$, $i7, \dots, i10 \Rightarrow j2$, $i11, \dots, i14 \Rightarrow j3$ and $i15, \dots, i18 \Rightarrow j4$.

7.2 L2 profile simulation

After, FL2S performed in a loop over individual L2 across track bins and call the core routine *fl2s.py* with the following steps:

1. Interpolation of *ak2d*, *apriori*, *correlated_noise*, *sys_tot_sample_corr*, and *sys_tot_sample_uncorr* to day-of-year (*doy*) and solar activity level (*sol*), corresponding to the actual day.
2. Loop over along track positions in which the following operations are performed:
 - a. Interpolation *ak2d*, *correlated_noise*, *sys_tot_sample_corr*, and *sys_tot_sample_uncorr* to the latitude and solar zenith angle (*sza*) of the actual along-track position i .
 - b. Computation of the retrieval response $X_i = \mathbf{A}_i (\mathbf{X}_m - \mathbf{X}_a) + X_{ai}$, where X_i is a vector of dimension n_z , \mathbf{X}_m and \mathbf{X}_a are the model truth and a priori fields, respectively, around i (a vector of dimension $m \times n_z$), and X_{ai} is the a priori profile at i .
 - c. Computation of the correlated measurement noise error $\epsilon_{noise,i} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{r}$ (see Eq. (12)).
 - d. Computation of the across-track correlated systematic total error *sys_tot_sample_corr (icalc)* where *icalc* is an integer number in the range of the MC sample size which is randomly chosen for each calibration period. *icalc* is chosen to be the same across all tracks. Similarly, computation of the across-track uncorrelated systematic error *sys_tot_sample_uncorr*

(*icalu*), where *icalu* is chosen in the same manner as *icalc*, but drawn independently for each track. Both systematic error components are selected to be consistent for all targets on the same date.

The standard across-track binning (variable *act_bin* of the LPE output) applied in the LPE depends on the species and altitude. In many cases, the *act_bin* is 100 km below 50 km of altitude and switches to 300 km above in the mesosphere. For some other species, however, *act_bin* is 300 km also below 50 km of altitude, like for CO or SF₆. By default, FL2S uses 100 km ACT bins (i.e., the minimum bin size provided by the LPE) for all altitudes, resulting in 4 tracks for the 400 km swath width. To account for reduced (e.g., 300 km) ACT binning, two solutions have been implemented. In the first solution, the first 3 and the last 3 tracks are averaged to two overlapping 300-km tracks, which are replicated to be consistent with the 4 track setup. Since the noise and the spatially uncorrelated systematic errors have been estimated for 300-km binning, and since random errors computed by the FL2S are spatially uncorrelated for each 100 km wide track, the averaging procedure reduces those effects by a factor of $\sqrt{3}$. To counteract that reduction in errors by averaging, the noise part and the spatially uncorrelated part of the systematic error are multiplied by $\sqrt{3}$ in places where the tracks are averaged to emulate a coarser ACT binning. In this solution, the user must be aware that values in tracks 1 and 2 are the same, as well as for track 3 and 4, thus having to use only track 1 and 3 (or 2 and 4 or 2 and 3). This is problematic if L2 profiles are to be assimilated. In this case, the second solution is to skip the averaging of the first 3 and the last 3 tracks. It results in different L2 profiles in the four tracks and the user can always get the 300 km ACT resolution by averaging the first 3 and the last 3 tracks a posteriori. However, the L2 error profiles must be multiplied by $\sqrt{3}$ otherwise data assimilation system will provide too large confidence in the L2 profiles given on 300 km ACT resolution. Note however that this mode can only be applied to chemical species, not on the temperature.

Note that FL2S does use a priori information only in the simulation of L2 temperature profiles, not for the chemical species.

Since constituent retrievals simulated with the LPE are always performed in a vmr parameter space (with unit ppmv), averaging kernels and error budgets in FL2S are also expressed in terms of volume mixing ratios. To apply FL2S to derived quantities such as aerosol volume density, those have to be converted to vmr-like quantities first with the routines provided within the program.

7.3 Cloud masking

Infrared limb spectra are strongly influenced by the presence of clouds. On one hand, this sensitivity can be exploited to extract valuable information on cloud properties (e.g. thin cirrus clouds, aerosols, and polar stratospheric clouds (PSCs) (see[10])). On the other hand, clouds can degrade the retrieval of atmospheric temperature and trace gas concentrations by obscuring parts of the atmosphere and introducing radiative artifacts that can significantly degrade the quality of the products.

To reduce the effects of cloud contamination, a cloud detection and filtering strategy—similar to that used for the MIPAS mission—has to be applied in the Level 2 (L2) processing, in particular cloud-affected scans are identified and excluded prior to L2 processing.

For MIPAS, retrievals were limited to regions above the cloud top height. Unlike one-dimensional retrieval systems, CAIRT employs a two-dimensional (2D) retrieval approach, using data from multiple contiguous lines of sight. This raises the need for a more rigorous assessment of how clouds affect the retrievals in a 2D context.

As detailed in [11], the impact of cloud contamination on 2D Level 2 (L2) retrievals was assessed under the assumption that all spectra potentially affected by clouds—i.e., those corresponding to lines of sight intersecting the clouds—are excluded from the analysis. Specifically:

- Clouds are defined as occupying specific points within the 2D retrieval grid.
- All spectral points associated with non-zero elements in the CAIRT 2D Jacobian with respect to these cloud-covered grid points are removed. This represents a conservative approach, as no threshold is applied to define when a Jacobian element is considered 'effectively zero.' However, this also implies that potential scattering effects from cloud-adjacent regions—i.e., spectra influenced by clouds not directly intersected by the line of sight—, effects that are generally smaller than the effects of absorption for small scattering particles, are not accounted for.
- The 2D Averaging Kernel (AK) and Covariance Matrix (CM) for the retrieved species (e.g., ozone) are then recomputed using only the remaining, uncontaminated spectra.

Figure 8 shows the results for eight different cloud extents. The white rectangle denotes the cloud location. The blue area (value = 1) identifies regions where the AK ratio (cloudy vs. clear-sky) is below 0.8, indicating degraded performance but still usable data. The green area highlights regions where the diagonal AK values are below 0.003 in the cloudy case, indicating that no useful information can be retrieved. It can be clearly seen that the regions with no useful information strongly depend on the vertical and horizontal extension of the cloud.

Figure 8 Areas where CAIRT performances are degraded due to clouds of 8 different extensions as indicated in the title of each plot and as represented by the white rectangle (the white rectangle connects the external points of the retrieval grid in correspondence of the cloud). Two different areas are highlighted: the blue area (value =1) is the one where the ratio between diagonal elements of AK in the cloudy case and the one in clear-sky is smaller than 0.8: this represents the region where performances are degraded but measurements still possible. The green area is the region where diagonal elements of AK of the cloudy case are smaller than 0.003, so no measurements are possible.

To implement a cloud masking strategy in the FL2S simulator using realistic cloud scenarios, a method was needed to represent the effect of extended cloud fields along the satellite orbit as the sum of localized clouds at each grid point. This approach was found to be possible only when clouds have a vertical extent starting from the CAIRT lowest tangent altitude (columnar cloud). On the contrary, this approach could not be applied for clouds with limited vertical thickness, where retrievals beneath the cloud may still be possible. The conservative choice of assuming all columnar clouds was adopted.

The file *cloud_impact_cth5-22_0.003.dat* provides the masking data used to filter out contaminated L2 products. For each cloud top height (CTH) from 5 to 22 km, it contains the corresponding mask—defined as a function of altitude and along-track distance—that identify regions where retrievals are not reliable. These masks correspond to the green areas in Figure 9, where the averaging kernel (AK) falls below 0.003, indicating insufficient sensitivity for meaningful retrievals.

Figure 9 Extension of the area affected by a column cloud extending from 5 km to different Cloud Top Heights as indicated in the title of each map.

These masks are applied post-simulation by FL2S of the L2 products, in order to exclude data that would not be retrievable due to cloud contamination. The masking is based on realistic cloud coverage for the

specific scenario, assuming columnar cloud structures with the cloud top heights (CTH) being provided at each point of the along track grid by the model.

7.4 Program installation and usage

The main FL2S code, `fl2s_run.py`, is stored on the FZJ github CAIRT repository: https://jugit.fz-juelich.de/cairt-scirec/cairt_fl2s.

No special install procedure is required, but the program depends on python3 and the following packages: `cftime` for handling time and date conversions, `netCDF4` for reading and writing netcdf files, `numpy` and `scipy` for array operations and scientific calculations, and `xarray` for handling data sets.

These packages can be installed in a local environment with `pip`:

```
> pip install -r requirements.txt
```

Help to run `fl2s_run.py` can be obtained by

```
> fl2s_run.py --help
```

FL2S can provide netCDF file in two different formats, the default format and the mode to prepare NetCDF Observation file format for BASCOE. Note that in both cases, the initial seed value for random number generation is saved in each daily FL2S output file to ensure reproducibility.

7.4.1 Running FL2S in default mode

To run FL2S in default mode, edit `config.py` based on the examples provided within the file. Then run it with python:

```
> python fl2s_run.py ./config.py
```

The scenario setup in `config.py` includes file locations, science cases, and selected trace gases and dates. The important entries are:

- `para2ref`: Python dictionary containing the target name and the final part of the LPE output netcdf file name
- `lpe_ncdir`: Full path to the directory containing the LPE output netcdf files
- `CSSn`: The scenario name, as set up with `css_config` below
- `mod_ncdir`: Full path to the directory containing the scene input
- `sol_activity`: Solar activity index (within 0 for low activity and 1 for high activity). The default is 0.
- `n_cal`: Calibration period length (in terms of acquisitions). The default is 100. The value recommended in the MRD is 56.
- `akd_threshold`: Averaging kernel threshold. The default is 0.003.
- `ak_noise_sys`: Python dictionary containing the output variables and the respective noise components to include.
- `act_bin_ind`: Python dictionary for the across-track bins
- `random_seed_method`: Method to use for initializing the random number generators for the noise and systematic error components, it is not advisable to use anything other than "auto"

- ``random_seed``: Value to add to the number determined by ``random_seed_method`` for extra randomness.
- ``nmod_use``: For testing, set to a positive number to calculate only so many samples along-track, use a negative number for all along-track samples
- ``css_config``: Python dictionary describing the different "CSSn" scenarios, each one containing
 - o ``cdate_l``: List of dates as strings in the format "yyyymmdd"
 - o ``para_soll``: List of target names, each one must be included in ``para2ref``
 - o ``mod_ncbasefil``: Basename of the model data file

In this default mode, CAIRT L2 TDS-P files in netCDF format are given, with one file per day per L2 product. The list of dimensions and the list of variables in NetCDF files are given, respectively, Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5: List of dimensions in daily TDS-P CAIRT L2 netCDF files.

Dimension name	Description
time	The number of profiles available in the file, changing in each daily file
altitude	The number of levels, constant for each daily file
track	The number of tracks, constant for each daily file

Table 6: List of variables included in daily TDS-P CAIRT L2 netCDF files.

Variable name	Dimensions	Units	Description
time	time	days since 2000-01-01	Time of profile
lev	lev	km	Altitude of profile
lat_avg	time, track	degree_north	latitude of profile
lon_avg	time, track	degree_east	longitude of profile
temperature	time, track, altitude	K	Input scene temperature profiles after rebinning
pressure	time, track, altitude	Pa	Input scene pressure profiles after rebinning
cc	time, track, altitude	none	Input scene cloud fraction profiles after rebinning
TARG_ori	time, track, altitude	mol/mol	TARG input scene of profile after rebinning
TARG_ak	time, track, altitude	mol/mol	TARG_ori after application of AK
TARG_aknoi	time, track, altitude	mol/mol	TARG_ak + noise error
TARG_aksys	time, track, altitude	mol/mol	TARG_ak + systematic error
TARG_aknoisys	time, track, altitude	mol/mol	TARG_ak + noise error + systematic error
cloud_mask	time, track, altitude	none	0=valid value; 1=masked by cloud

TARG stands for temperature or a chemical species for which an LPE file exists (O₃, H₂O, ...). For chemical species, the variables TARG will start with ``vmr_``.

7.4.2 Running FL2S to get NOB file format

In this case, FL2S will provide L2 file in the NetCDF Observation file format for BASCOE (NOB). This format, used by the BASCOE assimilation system, request ``time`` and ``lev`` dimensions, and for each chemical species, the L2 profiles, the associated L2 error profiles and profiles of quality_flag.

To produce CAIRT NOB files, edit ``config_nob.py`` based on the examples provided within the file. Then run ``fl2s_run.py`` with several options:

```
> python fl2s_run.py -A -f input_scene_filename -o output_L2_filename config_nob.py
```

assuming the input scene does include data for only one day (or a part of one day). In this case, the date will be taken in the input scene file. Providing the output L2 filename ensure to merge the difference L2 profiles for different species in a single files (temperture will not be updated by FL2S in this case). Files for each species will be created in temporary folder given `scratch` that should be defined in the config.py. The important entries in config.py are:

- `lpe_ncdir`: Full path to the directory containing the LPE files
- `n_cal`: Calibration period length (in terms of acquisitions). The default is 100. The value recomanded in the MRD is 56.
- `akd_threshold`: Averaging kernel threshold. The default is 0.003.
- `ak_noise_sys`: Python dictionary containing the output variables and the respective noise components to include.
- `act_bin_ind`: Python dictionary for the across-track bins
- `random_seed_method`: Method to use for initializing the random number generators for the noise and systematic error components, it is not advisable to use anything other than "auto"
- `random_seed`: Value to add to the number determined by `random_seed_method` for extra randomness.
- `nmod_use`: For testing, set to a positive number to calculate only so many samples along-track, use a negative number for all along-track samples
- `cld_fraction_lim`: the cloud fraction value above which L2 profile will be masked by cloud contamination. Works only if the variable `cc` is present in the input scene file.
- `cld_impact_file`: the cloud impact scenario file.
- `scratch`: path to an existing temporary folder where temporary file will be created. Must be clean by the user after having run FL2S.
- `CSSn`: While this value is not used in the NOB configuration, a value must be present.
- `css_config`: While not used, it should in contain an empty dictionary labelled by the value given in `CSSn`.

In the chemical data assimilation mode, CAIRT L2 TDS-P files in netCDF format are given, with one file per days. The list of dimensions and the list of variables in NetCDF files are given, respectively, Table 7 and Table 8.

Table 7: List of dimensions in daily TDS-P CAIRT L2 netCDF files.

Dimension name	Description
time	The number of profiles available in the file, changing in each daily file
lev	The number of levels, constant for each daily file
track	The number of tracks, constant for each daily file

Table 8: List of variables included in daily TDS-P CAIRT L2 netCDF files.

Variable name	Dimensions	Units	Description
time	time	days since 2000-01-01	Time of profile
altitude	lev	km	Altitude of profile
latitude	time, track	degree_north	latitude of profile
longitude	time, track	degree_east	longitude of profile
temperature	time, lev, track	K	Input scene temperature profiles after rebinning
pressure	time, lev, track	Pa	Input scene pressure profiles after rebinning

cc	time, lev, track	None	Input scene cloud fraction profiles after rebinning
vmr_ori_TARG	time, lev, track	mol/mol	Input scene profile after rebinning
vmr_TARG	time, lev, track	mol/mol	L2 profile for species TARG
vmr_err_TARG	time, lev, track	mol/mol	L2 error profile for species TARG
vmr_noi_TARG	time, lev, track	mol/mol	Contribution of noise error in L2 profile
vmr_sys_TARG	time, lev, track	mol/mol	Contribution of systematic error in L2 profile
vmr_apr_TARG	time, lev, track	mol/mol	L2 a priori profile for species TARG
vmr_cap_TARG	time, lev, track	mol/mol	Contribution of a priori in L2 profile
quality_flag_TARG	time, lev, track	1	quality flag (0=valid value, 1=mask by cloud, 2=below CAIRT lower altitude (5 km))

TARG stands for chemical species for which an LPE file exists (O₃, H₂O, ...).

8 Superobservations

CAIRT L2 files produced by FL2S have an ALT resolution of 50 km and an ACT resolution of 100 km leading to 4 tracks. These are large datasets that can lead to problem in data assimilation. For example, EnKF system like BASCOE has a memory fault error when trying to assimilated CAIRT simulated L2 profiles because the size of a matrix that the EnKF has to invert is too large. This is a well-known problem in data assimilation where the solution is to build superobservations [12], [13], [14]. In this setup, observations inside the same model grid cell for the same model time step are aggregated as follows. Consider N L2 profiles y_i and their associated uncertainty e_i available at the same model time step and within the same grid cell. The L2 superprofile s and its associated uncertainty σ is calculated as follows:

$$s = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N y_i$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N (e_i)^2}.$$

For this procedure, a new code has been created, `mk_superobs.py`. It takes on input a daily CAIRT NOB file, the model resolution which will assimilated CAIRT “superprofiles” and the filename where to store CAIRT L2 “superprofiles”. This code is stored on the FZJ github CAIRT repository: https://jugit.fz-juelich.de/cairt-scirec/cairt_superobs, is calling as follows:

```
> ./mk_superobs.py -Ovr NLONxNLAT_model_resolution -o CAIRT_L2super_filename CAIRT_NOB_filename.
```

This code also allows to create CAIRT superobservation by removing one (or more) of the contribution from the noise (noi) error, systematic (sys) error and the contribution of the a priori (cap, as long as FL2S used a priori in his computation), since these contribution are stored in CAIRT NOB files):

To get all the contribution (default):

```
> ./mk_superobs.py -Ovr NLONxNLAT -o CAIRT_L2super_filename -u noi+sys CAIRT_NOB_filename
```

To get, e.g., only the contribution of the noi error:

```
> ./mk_superobs.py -Ovr NLONxNLAT -o CAIRT_L2super_filename -u noi CAIRT_NOB_filename
```

Superobservation files are formatted in NOB format, with one file per days. The list of dimensions and the list of variables in these files are given, respectively, in Table 9 and Table 10.

Table 9: List of dimensions in daily superobservation netCDF files.

Dimension name	Description
time	The number of profiles available in the file, changing in each daily file
lev	The number of levels, constant for each daily file

Table 10: List of variables included in daily superobservation netCDF files.

Variable name	Dimensions	Units	Description
time	time	days since 2000-01-01	Time of profile
lev	lev	km	Altitude of profile
lat_avg	time	degree_north	latitude of profile
lon_avg	time	degree_east	longitude of profile
temperature	time, lev	K	NR temperature profiles after regridding in sect. 2.2-2.4 ¹
pressure	time, lev	Pa	NR pressure profiles after regridding in sect. 2.2-2.4 ¹
vmr_TARG	time, lev	mol/mol	TARG profiles after steps in sect. 2.1-2.4
vmr_err_TARG	time, lev	mol/mol	TARG error profiles taken from FL2S and LPE
quality_flag_TARG	time, lev	1	TARG quality flag

TARG stands for chemical species for which an LPE file exists (O₃, H₂O, ...).

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